

The influence of physical activity on the quality life amongst cancer patients

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Abstract

Current forecasts indicate that the number of patients with cancer diagnosed over the preceding five years will reach approximately 75 million in 2030. Cancer affects not only the physical condition of the patient but also, to a significant extent, the psychological well-being. Medical progress in the field of oncology has been focused on methods that will allow for increasingly earlier detection of cancer, successful treatment and subsequent recovery of the patient. Increasing importance is also being given to improving the psychological well-being of patients, which has a considerable impact on their diagnosis, treatment and further rehabilitation. The psycho-physical equilibrium in the patient's struggle with such a severe disease is extremely important and may have a positive influence on the entire procedure. Cancer, like many other chronic diseases, may have an unpredictable course, which might be beyond the control of both the medical personnel and even the most compliant of patients. Therefore, physiotherapists should motivate patients by indicating the benefits of therapies while maintaining certain neutrality. They must never promise something they are not sure to achieve. However, it is worth taking the time to develop a suitable, individual course of activities with each patient, because numerous studies demonstrate that such an approach leads to the improvement of the patient's physical and psychological condition. What seems to be of the greatest significance in assessing the influence of physical exercise on the cancer patients' quality of life is not the improvement of their physical and psychological condition alone, but also the issue of safety. It should be underlined and promoted that physiotherapy, if properly selected and conducted, offers a safe, healthy and mood-enhancing alternative for cancer patients.

Key words: quality of life, cancer patient, oncology physiotherapy

Introduction

Nowadays, more than 12.5 million cancers are diagnosed annually worldwide, with the mortality rate reaching 7.6 million individuals per year. The development of medicine is making cancer therapies increasingly effective and numerous treatment-related side effects, such as nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite, diarrhoeas, muscular pains (myalgia), depression, fatigue etc., can also be minimised by regular exercise [1,2]. Unfortunately, the road to combat cancer is still long, difficult and strewn with obstacles. Even though the methods are better than several years ago, the treatment continues to exert negative (both short-term and long-term) effects on the physical and mental condition of patients. Pain, reduced cardiorespiratory performance, fatigue, lower quality of life and decreased function of the immune system are some of the numerous adverse events that patients must often face [3].

Physical activity is extremely important not only in the case of cancer prevention, but also for patients already diagnosed with cancer. Regular exercise can offer a number of benefits during the whole life of a cancer patient. However, patients post-treatment run the risk of a sedentary lifestyle due to fatigue and debilitation. The human body and its physical aspects, together with the

broadly conceived psychological dimension, form an inseparable whole, which constantly undergoes complicated and interlinked life processes [4]. Therefore, physiotherapy of cancer patients should encompass both their physical and psychological planes. It is only through a balance between these two realms that a therapy can be oriented towards success and help.

A cancer patient

The term "cancer patient" seems to be very simple. It is an individual who has been diagnosed with cancer. However, this is not the whole truth. Over 10 million Americans have been diagnosed with cancer at least once in their lifetime [5]. The WHO estimates that 12.5 new cases of cancer were recorded in 2008, with 28 million people already living with the disease. Further forecasts indicate that the number of patients with cancer diagnosed over the preceding five years will reach approximately 5 million in 2030 [6]. Will each of these individuals be classified as the above-mentioned "cancer patient"? There is no precise answer to this question. Cancer sufferers include patients with an active/ongoing malignant disease, patients with active cancer receiving treatment, patients without clinical symptoms of the disease receiving adjuvant therapy, patients at an advanced stage of

Diagram 1. Structure of death causes in Poland Source: own work on the basis of [8].

cancer undergoing palliative treatment, advanced stage cancer sufferers at the end of life, patients who completed their therapies and survived one month, six months, as well as those who completed their cancer treatment many years ago. One must also remember about individuals who have not been diagnosed yet – they are cancer patients who are unaware of their disease. As a rule, the term “cancer patient” is used to describe both patients with an active neoplastic disease and those who have undergone a successful therapy. However, the latter – especially long-term survivors – are often treated as cases that are more similar to the “normal healthy population” compared with patients with active malignancy [7]. Currently, cancer is the second most common cause of deaths in Poland (Diagram 1).

Cancers are forecast to become the most common cause of deaths in Poland over the coming decade.

Quality of life, diagnosis and the treatment process

The quality of life (QOL) is defined in a number of ways. However, it is not possible to choose the single best definition. One of the most commonly quoted definitions is “a state of well-being that is a composite of two components: (1) the ability to perform everyday activities

that reflect physical, psychological, and social well-being and (2) patient satisfaction with levels of functioning and the control of disease and/or treatment-related symptoms” [9]. The definition reflects several areas of theoretical agreement in defining QOL [10,11]. However, it should be borne in mind that the quality of life is as individual as every one of us is and every single person could write his or her own definition by specifying what determines and affects the given QOL. What is essential is the fact that the quality of life contains all the aspects of a human life – physical, psychological, spiritual, social and economic.

Being diagnosed with cancer is always a huge shock. An individual is suddenly thrown into a situation in which s/he needs not only to adapt in terms of life reorganisation – e.g. resignation from work, minimising or abandoning daily activities for hospitalisation, numerous formalities related to the organisation of the treatment itself and the insurance-related issues – but also to adjust mentally to cope with the entirely new situation. Patients are faced with more than just the obvious questions about death, the treatment process or finances. Some also worry about the consequent hair loss or the necessity to have their limb amputated, while others are gripped by doubts concerning the meetings with their friends and relatives as well as their social life (Diagram 2).

Diagram 2. Cancer survivorship

Source: Own work on the basis of Ferrell B.R., Grant M. City of Hope Beckman Research Institute (2004)

Cancer sufferers, of course, also ask about how much the diagnosis will affect their lives and whether the disease or treatment will be painful [7].

The link between the symptoms of the disease, life satisfaction, the feeling of health and the actual functioning of the patient is very complicated. It is also quite significant to underline the influence of the patient's individual characteristics and the environment in which s/he functions. Patients with diagnosed cancer are informed by their physician about the changes they should expect and which may result from the disease or the corresponding treatment. Moreover, they will often receive information about the time-frames in which they should expect a given situation to occur. However, such information will have a different meaning for each patient. The quality of life may be significantly reduced when the patient's expectations are confronted with the reality and prove to be completely different. An example is a patient who begins receiving physiotherapy following a surgery. Having completed an intensive cancer treatment, patients most often realise that they will be debilitated, fatigued and even a small dose of physical activity will be problematic. However, they assume that regular participation in the therapy will help them gradually improve their physical fitness. If patients recover faster than they expected, this has a strong influence on their motivation, perception and attitude towards the rehabilitation, thereby increasing

their quality of life. The situation becomes more complicated when patients feel no improvement or it occurs at a slower speed than they expected. This has a strong and significant negative impact on their quality of life. It is also essential to remember that there is a certain time interval between the commencement of the therapy and its potential influence on the quality of life [12].

The most significant principle is that physiotherapists must never promise their patients something they are not sure to achieve. It is obvious that the physiotherapist's voice and attitude during rehabilitation should be positive and cheerful, but at the same time – neutral. The duty of physiotherapists is to encourage their patients to actively participate in the therapy and present them with all the benefits and advantages that may emerge. However, it is also necessary to warn the patients that every single individual reacts to the treatment and rehabilitation in a different manner and inform them about the possible side effects. Patients should also receive clear and transparent explanations that the improvement process is often long-lasting, the effects are not always visible at once, and that they must get fully involved, often demonstrating not only patience but huge effort as well. Planning oncological rehabilitation and presenting it to patients is extremely difficult and requires many years of experience in order for the physiotherapist to be able to inform the patients about the importance of

physiotherapy and its positive effects, without raising hope and confidence in the patients about something that cannot be guaranteed. Cancer, like many other chronic diseases, may have an unpredictable course, which might be beyond the control of both the medical personnel and even the most compliant of patients. It is absolutely unacceptable to console the patients and tell them that everything will work out for the better only to improve their mood at a given moment. When their health suddenly deteriorates, it is quite likely that they will not be able to cope with this situation because “it was supposed to be better” and they did comply with all the recommendations. A safer option for patients is to make them realise that not everything can be predicted, but the treatment and therapy they will be offered are selected in the best manner possible.

Each member of the healthcare personnel should remember that the treatment of patients does not only involve surgeries, physiotherapies, medications or injections. It is also extremely important to take care of the psychological dimension of the treatment. Poor psychological condition, permanent anxiety, fear and misunderstanding may have a negative effect on and effectively hinder the treatment process. It is therefore vital that patients be treated as a “whole”. Due to the recent scientific reports proving the importance of patients’ well-being and quality of life, healthcare personnel are starting to put an emphasis on the need to support patients. Sometimes such activities as a mere conversation with patients, listening or smiling to them are more effective than purely medical procedures, for example drug administration. Hence the approach to patients is extremely important in the case of physiotherapists, who often spend many hours with their patients during rehabilitation. Cooperation from and positive attitude of the patients, which can be achieved through exercising, can significantly impact on the entire treatment process.

Cancer patients and physical activity – living, not just surviving

It is crucial to understand the key concepts of physical activity and exercise. Physical activity is defined as any bodily movement initiated by the work of skeletal muscles that increases energy expenditure beyond the basal level [13]. Physical activity encompasses all bodily movements, from typing on a keyboard to housekeeping activities to structured exercise routines. Free-living physical activity refers to activities that occur within the confines of daily living. Exercise, on the other hand, is a specific type of physical activity, consisting of selected, repetitive body movements focused on a specific goal – to improve or maintain physical fitness [13]. The most common types of exercise include aerobic, strength training

and stretching. This, however, does not change the fact that the first training sessions in heavily debilitated cancer patients will be oriented towards the everyday activities.

The desired health benefits are dependent on the training programme that has been chosen. Different types of exercise programmes result in different outcomes. For example, aerobic exercise promotes cardiorespiratory fitness by engaging large muscle groups in a continuous, rhythmic fashion [14]. Strength training with progressive resistance builds muscle mass and enhances muscle strength and endurance in the specific areas of the body being trained [15]. Even though aerobic exercise is effective in the improvement of cardiorespiratory fitness, strength training more effectively minimises muscle atrophy associated with prolonged physical inactivity.

What seems to be of the greatest significance in assessing the influence of physical exercise on the cancer patients’ quality of life is not the improvement of their physical and psychological condition alone, but also the issue of safety [16, 17, 18]. It should be underlined and promoted that physiotherapy, if properly selected and conducted, offers a safe, healthy and mood-enhancing alternative. Currently, there is an increasing body of literature and scientific research describing this subject [19, 20, 21].

Despite the multitude of studies examining this issue, the main emphasis is placed on the pure fact that physiotherapy is helpful [22]. However, the question that remains to be answered is what type of exercises would be the most suitable for cancer patients in order to achieve concrete effects.

The US Department of Health and Human Services recommends that healthy individuals, for substantial health benefits, should do at least 150 minutes (2 hours and 30 minutes) a week of moderate-intensity or 75 minutes (1 hour and 15 minutes) a week of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity, or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity aerobic activity. Aerobic activity should be performed in episodes of at least 10 minutes, and preferably, it should be spread throughout the week. According to the American College of Sports Medicine, cancer survivors should perform aerobic exercise for 20 to 60 minutes a day. Each patient – depending on their weight, health and fitness, and age – should receive a custom-made training programme. Resistance training for the whole body should last less than one hour, while stretching exercises should each time be incorporated into the training [23].

The available literature and websites contain a number of sample training programmes. However, specialist knowledge is required for the procedures to be safe, correct and centred on a cancer patient. Developing a

Diagram 3. Components of the training session

Source: own work on the basis of [13].

physiotherapy programme is connected with the knowledge about the specific type of cancer, its treatment and the expected recovery. Unfortunately, there is no single, universal source which would inform us how such a rehabilitation programme should be created. Despite the growing body of research on the particular cancers and types of therapies, data are still insufficient to develop a suitable protocol for a given case. The aspects that need to be taken into consideration while preparing a suitable physiotherapy protocol have been presented in Diagram 3.

The intensity of exercising reflects how much a given activity impacts on the body. The mode of exercising, on the other hand, indicates the type of exercise performed. Duration informs us about the time or number of repetitions of episodes recommended in the training. Frequency provides information about the number of days in a week, on which the training session must be incorporated, while progress indicates the optimal level of physical effort which should be achieved within the specified time-frame. Progress is essential not only due to the fact that it allows us to assess the therapeutic procedures in a given patient, but it also makes it possible to plan further training sessions, for example by increasing the weight, raising the number of repetitions or extending the duration of the whole programme.

A successful rehabilitation programme is not only one which is tailor-made to the individual needs of a given patient, but it must also encourage him/her to participate in it. What seems to be of crucial importance at the very beginning is to establish the goal of the rehabilitation procedure. This goal must be clear, yet achievable,

which will make it easier for the physiotherapist to develop a proper training plan and motivate the patient. In the case of a healthy population, the goals are focused on numerous aspects, including the improvement of physical fitness, enhancement of muscle strength, increase in muscle mass, stretching or body sculpting. Cancer patients often define their goals in a much clearer manner. They focus on recovery through physical activity, alleviation of the symptoms of their disease and/or the accompanying treatment, adaptation to the new situation also in a physical sense and improvement of the quality of their life. It should be remembered that every single individual has slightly different needs. The needs and goals of each cancer patient will also be different due to the fact that the disease may have a different course and affect virtually every single organ in the body. A patient who has had one lung removed will try to improve his/her physical fitness, while a woman after mastectomy may pay particular attention to the oedemas of the upper limb and their elimination – and both are cancer patients. It is important for every single improvement programme to consider not merely the main goal, but also the smaller ones that patients often care about. In order to achieve the overall positive goal of physiotherapy, it is worth focusing on the small steps that lead to its achievement. Particular emphasis should be put on cancer patients, where we need to remember about their psychological condition, past experiences with physical activity or even rehabilitation and the concomitant illnesses. A cancer patient does not have to suffer from oncological problems alone – s/he may also

Aerobic exercises	
Outdoors	Indoors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • walking, • jogging, • Nordic walking, • biking, • roller-skating, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • treadmill jogging; • swimming in a pool; • dancing, • aerobics; • aquatic aerobics.

Table 1. Examples of aerobic exercises

experience cardiological, neurological or orthopaedic deficits.

In the case of healthy individuals, there is a series of recommendations that can be used for the development of a proper training plan. However, a certain difficulty emerges in the case of cancer patients. As mentioned above, there are no specific protocols to be followed and the matter is further complicated by the presence of contraindications. Therefore, it is often a great challenge to develop a suitable programme for cancer patients. Each time, we do our best so that the rehabilitation process contains not only exercises, but also other activities that help the patients find satisfaction, enjoyment and positive attitude. There are many different types aerobic exercises available (Table 1).

Although all of these activities were successfully implemented in cancer patients, participation in some of them may be contraindicated in specific subgroups of cancer sufferers [24,25].

The same might be the case in the development of a strength training programme. However, it is worth taking the effort to create such a model of improvement, because many researchers proved the positive effects of strength training on building muscle mass in cancer patients [26, 27]. Strength training is mainly conducted in a gym or exercise facilities and involves weightlifting, specialist equipment or a Thera-Band.

Rehabilitation in chronic diseases, including cancer, is complicated and physiotherapists are not always able to prepare a training programme for every single patient to handle. Frequent mood swings, fatigue, side effects of the treatment, sudden health deteriorations or debilitation of the body require the training programme to be flexible and adjusted to the needs of each patient. According to the US Department of Health and Human Services, based on their fitness at a given moment, patients should be involved in such physical activities that are possible taking into consideration their physical capabilities and health condition. The main recommendation is

to avoid inactivity because “any physical activity is better than none”.

Summary

Taking into consideration statistical data, the number of cancer patients is expected to rise year after year. Cancer necessitates strict discipline, hard work and a huge dose of patience, during the diagnosis, in the course of treatment and afterwards. Patients are then exposed to enormous stress and come up with questions not only about pain or death but also about the aspects of everyday life. A very negative phenomenon, which is – in a sense – overshadowed by the prospect of cancer is the problem of professional work. As soon as they are diagnosed with cancer, employed individuals are faced with the fact of unemployment and, consequently, the reduction of income. Many professionally active people lost their jobs while struggling with cancer due to prolonged sick leave, thereby becoming financially dependent on their next of kin. Cancer not only ruins patients' health but often leads to a significant reduction in their material status. It is a disease that can remain silent or ‘dormant’ for many years after the treatment is completed. Therefore, it is crucial for patients to undergo regular medical check-ups to detect any potential recurrence as soon as possible. Cancer patients remain in this category throughout their lives, hence the importance of regular medical monitoring.

A positive aspect, however, is the fact that each coming year will bring improvements in medicine and its achievements. As a result, there is a great chance that neoplastic diseases will be diagnosed at increasingly earlier stages and successfully treated, with the post-treatment procedure being focused on the improvement of the patient's physical and psychological health. Strong emphasis in this regard is placed on physiotherapy, which can improve virtually every aspect of the patient's life. Despite the fact that developing a suitable rehabilitation regime continues to present a huge chal-

lenge, it can be undertaken and overcome through proper exercise planning, adequate resources (place, equipment and time) and creativity. Cooperation of the entire medical personnel is also of crucial importance. It should encompass oncologists, physiotherapists, nurses, psychologists and the patient's family. Concerted action for the benefit of the patient is the key to success.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.